

The future of pharmacy in Libya

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One must accept the complexity of modern society as a multifaceted influence which will direct the future of all social organizations. Technology has brought the people of the world into almost instant communication. Biomedical science has conquered most infectious, acute diseases and has provided several medicines for a successful maintenance therapy of chronic diseases. The life style of some people as smoking and drug addiction remain a strong factor to their achievement of health goals of the good life. Universally, economic inflation and international business have created an economic interdependence among nations and dealing of the economic problems of one country must take into account this interdependence. When one views the future within this technologic-social-economic framework, he has difficulty sorting out certain directing influences that may shape the future of pharmacy practice in Libya.

Currently, the duties, functions and roles undertaken by pharmacists in Libya range from those limited to traditional dispensing duties to highly clinically oriented roles [1]. In this regard, the Libyan health service providers request for the expanded roles of pharmacists in the society. Many of them ask for a number of clinical and patient-oriented functions as oncology, patient counseling, chronic care, hypertension, pediatric, diabetes, psychiatric, cardiology and others. They also question for protocols, standing orders and procedures for pharmacist management of drug therapy and provide information to use as a basis for initiation of clinically oriented services. The treatment of chronic diseases will be refined and drug therapy in many instances will be improved through the application of pharmacokinetic principles and improved methods of monitoring. There is no doubt that pharmacy practice has made clear steps in its own professionalization in hospitals during the past years. With an increase in the number of pharmacists practicing in hospitals and drug stores has come other changes in pharmacy manpower. Technicians and assistant pharmacists now perform many of the routine tasks in drug distribution under pharmacist's supervision. The latter, therefore, is available to participate in clinical programs in inpatient areas and in outpatient clinics. The practice of technicians and assistant pharmacists both in and out of hospitals remains a controversial issue in Libya (absence of a clear national medical policy).

Many pharmacists in Libya who provide services hold Bachelor degree in Pharmacy or Pharmaceutical Sciences or Doctor of Pharmacy (Pharm D) or have completed a short or long term diploma training in teaching hospitals or postgraduate academics. Some hold appointments in other health professions institutions. Libyan Association for Pharmacists (LAP) and Libyan Medical Board are currently planning for a program in clinical pharmacy in different clinical branches. Nevertheless, professional pharmacy personnel must be

upgraded in the future in both educational background and competence if continued professionalization is to be achieved [2]. The future will see continued stratification of professional personnel according to specialized functions in management and clinical and other professional; services particularly in large hospitals. The scope of the educational function of pharmacy will expand and become an increasingly important activity in the future in Libya. Some hospitals will maintain health education facilities as part of their physical plant. Others will participate in the program of area health education centers. Pharmacy's responsibility in this effort will require not only an increased commitment, but likewise, increased capability and capacity to provide educational services.

Conflict of interest: The author declares absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

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